

Quality Culture Framework Proposal for Libyan Industrial Companies

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Abstract : Libyan industrial companies face many challenges in today's competitive market. Quality management culture approaches is one of these challenges which may furnish the road to the Libyan industrial companies to effectively empower their employees and improve their ability to respond to the international competition. The primary objective of this paper is to design a practical approach to guide Libyan industrial companies toward successful quality culture implementation.

Keywords : TQM, quality culture, Libyan manufacturing industries, quality framework

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